

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF UV
SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS FOR THE ESTIMATION OF
DARUNAVIR IN BULK AND ITS PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE
FORM****M. M. Eswarudu*, P. Srinivasa Babu, P. Siva Krishna, G. Sneha Latha, N. Anusha,
M. S. K. Mounika and N. Punna Reddy.**Department of pharmaceutical Analysis & Quality Assurance, Vignan Pharmacy College,
Vadlamudi (V), Chebrolu (M), Guntur (Dist), Andhra Pradesh, India. 522213.**Abstract:**

Two simple, precise and economical UV Spectrophotometric methods have been developed for the estimation of Darunavir ethanolate (DRV) in bulk and its pharmaceutical dosage form. Two methods were developed based on measurement of absorption at maximum wavelengths, for Method I 272.1 nm and Method II 272.4 nm. Linearity for detector response was observed in the concentration range of 2-10 µg/ml for the both methods. The developed methods were validated with respect to linearity, accuracy (recovery), precision and specificity. The accuracy of the methods was assessed by recovery studies and was found to be 98.3% and 99% for Method I and Method II respectively. The results were validated statistically as per ICH Q2 R1 guidelines and were found to be satisfactory. The proposed methods were successfully applied for the determination of DRV in pharmaceutical dosage form.

Key words: *Darunavir, UV Spectrophotometry, Absorbance maxima methods and Validation.*

Corresponding Author:*M.M. Eswarudu,**

Assistant professor,

Department of pharmaceutical Analysis & Quality Assurance,

Vignan Pharmacy College,

Vadlamudi, Chebrolu (M), Guntur (Dist) - 522213,

Andhra Pradesh, India.

Email: eswarmunnangi@gmail.com

Mobile: 9553808484.

QR code

Please cite this article in press M.M. Eswarudu et al., *Method Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Methods for the Estimation of Darunavir in Bulk and Its Pharmaceutical Dosage Form*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(04).

INTRODUCTION:

Darunavir (Fig.1) is an antiviral drug and inhibitor of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) protease in adults and children 6 years of age and older [1]. It was approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) on June 23, 2006. Chemically it is [(3aS,4R,6aR)-2,3,3a,4,5,6a-hexahydrofuro[2,3-b]furan-4-yl]N-[(2S,3R)-4-[(4-aminophenyl)sulfonyl-(2-methylpropyl)amino]-3-hydroxy-1-phenylbutan-2-yl]carbamate. DRV, a second generation protease inhibitor, is discovered to overcome the problems with early protease inhibitor (PIs) like severe side effects and drug toxicities, require a high therapeutic dose, are costly to manufacture, and show a disturbing susceptibility to drug resistant mutations. DRV is used with ritonavir and other medications to treat HIV. It works by slowing the spread of HIV in the body. DRV selectively inhibits the cleavage of HIV-1 encoded Gag- Pol polyproteins in infected cells, thereby preventing the formation of mature virus particles[2]. DRV was designed to form robust interactions with the protease enzyme from many strains of HIV, including strains from treatment-experienced patients with multiple resistance mutations to PIs. It blocks HIV protease, an enzyme which is needed for HIV to multiply. HIV infection destroys CD4 (T) cells, which are important to the immune system. The immune system helps fight infection. Reducing the amount of HIV and increasing the CD4 (T) cell count may improve your immune system and, thus, reduce the risk of death or infections that can happen when your immune system is weak (opportunistic infections). Darunavir is co-administered with ritonavir and with other antiretroviral agents, is indicated for the treatment of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV-1) infection [3].

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Darunavir

Literature survey revealed that a few Spectrophotometric [4-11], HPLC [12-28], LC-MS [29-32], HPTLC [33] and electrophoresis [34] methods were reported earlier for the determination of Darunavir in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. The objective of the present study is to develop two simple, accurate, precise, economic

methods for the estimation of Darunavir in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. Validate the developed methods according to ICH guidelines [35].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals: Darunavir was generous gift samples from MARS Therapeutics and Chemicals Ltd. Hyderabad, India. Commercial tablets with brand name, Prezista (Janssen Pharmaceutical Limited) containing 300 mg was purchased from local Pharmacy store and used within their shelf-life period. All chemicals and solvents are of analytical grade reagents were used in this study.

Equipments: Double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer (SYSTRONICS- 2203) with 1cm matched quartz cells was used for the measurement of absorbance. Electronic balance (Essay- AJ-220 L) 1mg Sensitivity was used for weighing the samples. Ultrasonicator (Citizen) and Class 'A' volumetric glassware's were used for this work

Selection of Solvent for Analysis: The drug was insoluble in chloroform but soluble in Methanol and 0.1N sodium hydroxide & distilled water. The stability of Darunavir was found to be 24 hours. In methanol the stability of Darunavir is less. At the end of these studies, Distilled water and 0.1N Sodium hydroxide were chosen as solvents for this study, because of the time gain while preparing solutions and cost saving by eliminating the purchase and disposal of organic solvents.

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Method I: 10 mg of Darunavir was weighed and transferred to 100 ml of clean and dry volumetric flask and dissolved in distilled water and the solution was made up to volume 100 ml with distilled water to get 100 µg/ml of Darunavir. Method II: 10 mg of Darunavir was weighed and transferred to 100 ml of clean and dry volumetric flask and dissolved in 0.1N NaOH and the solution was made up to volume 100 ml with 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution to get 100 µg/ml of Darunavir.

Determination of Absorption Maxima (λ_{max}):

Standard solutions of Darunavir 10 µg /ml were prepared in two 10 ml volumetric flasks and each one diluted by Distilled water and 0.1N Sodium hydroxide. The above solutions were scanned over the range of 200 nm to 400 nm against reagent blank. The Maximum Absorbance of Darunavir at 272.1nm and 272.4 nm for method I and method II. UV Spectra of Method I and Method II were shown in Figure 3 & Figure 4.

Calibration curve: Aliquots (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 ml) of prepared standard stock solution were transferred into series of 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted by distilled water and 0.1N Sodium hydroxide to give the concentration range of 2-10 µg/ml. The above solutions were taken the absorbance values at 272.1nm and 272.4 nm. Calibration curves were prepared by plotting absorbance vs. concentration.

Estimation of Darunavir in Tablets: For the analysis of tablet dosage form, twenty tablets of Prezista (300 mg) were ground to fine powdered and mixed thoroughly. A quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg of the drug was transferred in to Two 100 ml clean and dry volumetric flasks and dissolved in about 40 ml of distilled water and 40 ml of 0.1N Sodium hydroxide and sonicated to dissolve completely and volume was made with the same solvents. The above sample solution was filtered and suitably diluted to get concentrations of 10 µg/ml. Absorbance was recorded against the blank at 272.1 nm and 272.4 nm.

Method Validation:

The proposed method was validated according to the ICH guidelines which include linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ) and robustness. Under the validation study, the following parameters were studied.

Linearity: Linearity is the ability (within specified range) to obtain test results are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in the sample. Linearity is evaluated by visual inspection of plot of signal as a function of analyte concentration. If there is a linear relationship test results are calculated by regression line by method of least squares. Calibration curves were constructed by plotting absorbance vs. concentration of Darunavir for method I and Method II and the regression equations were calculated. The calibration curves of Darunavir for Method I and Method II were plotted over 6 different concentrations.

Accuracy: Accuracy of analytical method is 'measure of how close the experimental value to the true value' accuracy of the method was determined

by standard addition method. A known amount of standard drug is added to the fixed amount of pre-analysed injection solution. Percent recovery is calculated by comparing the area before and after addition of the standard drug. The standard addition method is performed at 50%, 100% and 150% level. The solutions are analysed in triplicate at each level as per the proposed method.

Precision: Precision is expressed as the closeness of agreement between a series of measurements obtaining from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample. Six replicate solutions of a known concentration of Darunavir 6 µg/ml for method I and Method II have been analyzed by taking the absorbances of them by UV Spectrophotometer on the same day. The intermediate precision was estimated by injecting samples prepared at the same concentrations on three different days by different operators. The absorbance's ratios of all readings were taken and standard deviation, % relative standard deviation (RSD), was calculated.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ): Limit of detection and limit of quantification of Darunavir were determined by calibration curve method. Solutions of method I and method II were prepared in linearity range and taken the absorbance's values in triplicate. Average absorbance's values of three analyses were plotted against concentration.

LOD and LOQ were calculated by using the following equations:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times N / B$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times N / B$$

Where

N is residual variance due to regression; B is the slope.

Robustness: The standard and samples of Darunavir were taken absorbance's values by changing the conditions like wavelength, pH of the solvent and composition of the solvent. There was no significant change in the parameters like detection wavelength of drug substance, absorbance values etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Fig. 3: Linearity curve of Darunavir in Method-II****Table 1: Linearity results of Darunavir in proposed methods**

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance	
		Method I	Method II
1	2	0.169	0.161
2	4	0.381	0.355
3	6	0.571	0.557
4	8	0.757	0.77
5	10	0.972	0.968

Table 2: Recovery studies results of proposed methods

S.No.	Spike Level	µg/ml Added	Method I			Method II		
			µg/ml Found	% recovery	Mean% recovery	µg/ml Found	% recovery	Mean% recovery
1	20	2	1.974	98.71	98.49	1.975	98.75	98.96
2	20	2	1.961	98.07		1.987	99.38	
3	20	2	1.974	98.71		1.975	98.95	
1	60	6	5.955	99.25	99.44	5.978	99.64	99.40
2	60	6	5.977	99.63		5.946	99.11	
3	60	6	5.966	99.45		5.967	99.46	
1	100	10	9.969	99.69	100.05	9.979	99.79	99.79
2	100	10	9.979	99.79		9.969	99.69	
3	100	10	10.04	100.4		9.986	99.89	

Table 3: Intra-day precision (Repeatability) data of proposed methods

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Method I Absorbance at 272.1 nm		Method II Absorbance at 272.4 nm	
		Morning	Evening	Morning	Evening
1	6	0.571	0.572	0.557	0.559
2	6	0.572	0.571	0.557	0.558
3	6	0.569	0.569	0.559	0.557
4	6	0.570	0.569	0.558	0.558
5	6	0.570	0.570	0.556	0.559
6	6	0.571	0.572	0.558	0.556
7	Avg	0.978	0.978	0.557	0.557
8	SD	0.0010	0.0013	0.0010	0.0011
9	%RSD	0.107	0.133	0.188	0.209

Table 4: Inter-day precision (Reproducibility) data of proposed methods

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Method I Absorbance at 272.1 nm			Method II Absorbance at 272.4 nm		
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
1	6	0.571	0.574	0.569	0.557	0.560	0.565
2	6	0.569	0.572	0.568	0.554	0.561	0.568
3	6	0.568	0.571	0.569	0.556	0.562	0.569
4	6	0.570	0.573	0.572	0.555	0.559	0.567
5	6	0.571	0.574	0.571	0.557	0.560	0.569
6	6	0.569	0.571	0.567	0.554	0.562	0.564
7	Avg	0.569	0.9814	0.569	0.555	0.506	0.567
8	SD	0.001	0.0013	0.0018	0.0013	0.0012	0.002
9	%RSD	0.2108	0.139	0.316	0.234	0.231	0.352

Table 5: Robustness studies results of proposed methods

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance					
		Method I			Method II		
		270.1nm	272.1nm	274.1nm	270.4nm	272.4nm	274.4nm
1	8	0.755	0.756	0.755	0.77	0.77	0.767
2	8	0.756	0.757	0.753	0.776	0.772	0.766
3	8	0.754	0.754	0.754	0.777	0.772	0.77
4	8	0.753	0.757	0.754	0.778	0.771	0.768
5	8	0.754	0.751	0.755	0.776	0.77	0.769
6	8	0.756	0.755	0.756	0.776	0.771	0.77
7	Avg	0.754	0.755	0.754	0.754	0.771	0.768
8	SD	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0010	0.0016
9	%RSD	0.0929	0.093	0.093	0.093	0.134	0.212

Table-6: Optical characteristics and Validation summary

S.No.	Optical characteristics	Observed values	
		Method I	Method II
1	Beer's law limit	2-10 µg/ml	2-10 µg/ml
2	Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.999	0.999
3	Regression equation	y = 0.0951x+0.001	Y=0.0957x+0.001
4	Slope (m)	0.099	0.101
5	Intercept (c)	0.024	0.046
6	Intra Day Precision	0.1072	0.1881
7	Inter Day precision	0.455	0.272
8	Mean % recovery	98.49-100.06	98.96-99.79
9	LOD	0.8 µg/ml	1.50 µg/ml
10	LOQ	2.42 µg/ml	4.55 µg/ml

Table 7: Assay results of Darunavir in Tablets

Formulation	Label Claim	Method 1	% Assay	Method II	% Assay
PREZISTA	300 mg/ tablet	297 mg/ tablet	99	295 mg/ tablet	98.3

Optimized methods were linear in the range of 2-10 µg/ml for Darunavir with correlation coefficient 0.999 for methods. Linear regression data for method I and method II were given in Table 1, the linearity curves of darunavir for method I and method II were shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3. The mean % recoveries of developed methods for Darunavir were found to be 98.49 % to 100.15 % and 98.96 % to 99.97 % for method I and method II respectively. From the recovery studies it was clear that the methods were accurate for quantitative estimation of darunavir in tablet dosage form, as the statistical results were within the acceptance range. The accuracy results were shown in Table 2. In intraday study, concentration of replicates of drug was calculated on the same day for two times. In inter-day study the concentration of drug were calculated on three successive days which expresses the laboratory variation in different days. In both intra and inter day precision study for the proposed methods % RSD was calculated and results were shown in Table 3 and Table 4. The limit of detection and limit of quantification of Darunavir by proposed methods were determined using calibration curves. The LOD and LOQ of Darunavir were found to be 0.8 µg/ml and 2.42. µg /ml and 1.5 µg/ml and 4.55 µg/ml for method I and method II respectively, which indicate the sensitivity of the methods. The % RSD values of robustness studies were found to be < 2% reveal that the method is robust enough was shown in Table 5.

Optical characteristics such as Beer's law limit (µg/ml), correlation coefficient, Regression equation, Slope (m), and Intercept (c) were calculated and shown in Table-6. Validated methods were applied for the determination of Darunavir in commercial formulations. The % assay was found to be 99 % and 98.3 % for method I and method II respectively. And assay results were shown in Table 7. These data show that the proposed methods are simple, economic, precise and sensitive for the determination of Darunavir in bulk and its pharmaceutical dosage forms.

CONCLUSION:

The proposed methods were simple, sensitive, and cost-effective. It was validated in terms of linearity accuracy, precision LOD and LOQ. The results are reproducible, and can be used successfully for the estimation of Darunavir in bulk and its pharmaceutical formulations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The authors are thankful to Dr. P.Srinivasa Babu, Principal of Vignan Pharmacy College and thankful to Management of Vignan Pharmacy College for providing all types of facilities for this research work and also thankful to MARS Therapeutics Pvt.Limited, Hyderabad, for providing the gift sample of the drug.

REFERENCES:

1. The Merck Index. 2006. 14th Edn. Merck Research Laboratories, Merck & Co., White House Station, NJ, USA, page no. 477.
2. McKeage K, Perry CM and Keam SJ. Darunavir. *Drugs*, 2009; 69(4):477-503.
3. Ghosh AK, Dawson ZL and Mitsuya H. Darunavir, a conceptually new HIV-1 protease inhibitor for the treatment of drug-resistant HIV. *Bio org Med Chem.*, 2007; 15(24):7576-7580.
4. Parameswara Rao K, Validation of Visible Spectrophotometric Methods of Darunavir in Pure and Dosage Forms. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2016; 8(17):54-61.
5. Vijayalakshmi R, Naga Sri Ramya Y, Dimple Mani A, and Dhanaraju M.D. Spectrophotometric Determination of Darunavir Ethanolate by Condensation Technique. *International Journal of Pharmtech Research*, 2016; 9(6):301-306.
6. Mrinalini Damle and Ajinkya Deosthali. UV-Spectrophotometric Absorbance Correction Method and Absorbance Ratio Method for the Simultaneous Estimation of Ritonavir and Darunavir Ethanolate. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Science*, 2016; 5(8):1179-1187.
7. Minal R. Ghante, Rohan S. Shelar, Sanjay D. Sawant, Manoj M. Kadam. Development and validation of UV Spectrophotometric method for estimation of darunavir ethanolate in bulk and tablet dosage form. *Int J Pharm Pharm. Sci*, 2014; 6(7): 240-242.
8. Say Sirisha. Vanukuri, Mastanamma Sk, Alekhya G. Validated UV-Spectrophotometric Methods for the Estimation of Darunavir by Absorption Maxima, First Order Derivative and Area under Curve in Bulk and Its Tablet Dosage Form. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2014; 6(1):568-571.
9. Shinde VR, Gosavi SA, Pawar SS, Kasture VS, Musmade DS and Shinde VR. Development and validation of UV spectroscopic method for determination of Darunavir in bulk and tablet formulation. *Inventi Rapid: Pharm Anal Qual Assur.*, 2013; 12:586.
10. Ana Carolina Kogawa, Hérica Regina Nunes Salgado. Development and Validation of Infrared Spectroscopy Method for the Determination of Darunavir in Tablets. *Physical Chemistry* 2013; 3(1):1-6.
11. Josilene Chaves Ruela Corrêa, Cristina Helena dos Reis Serra, Hérica Regina Nunes Salgado, Development and Validation of First Derivative Spectrophotometric Method for Quantification of Darunavir in Tablets. *SDI Paper*, 2012; 4(1):801-902.
12. Rao GA, Eswarudu MM, Devadasu Ch, and P.Srinivasa Babu. Novel RP-HPLC Method for the Determination of Darunavir in Pure and Tablet Dosage Form. *American Journal of PharmTech Research*, 2017; 7(1):255-266.
13. Mallikarjuna Rao N, Gowri sankar D. Simultaneous Quantification of Novel Antiretroviral Drug Combination by Stability-Indicating High Performance Liquid Chromatography Method. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2016; 78(6):755-762.
14. Venkata Siva Sri Nalini M, Rama Krishna Veni P, Hari Babu B. Determination Of Darunavir And Cobicistat Simultaneously Using Stability Indicating RP- HPLC Method. *Marmara Pharmaceutical Journal*, 2016; 20(4):293-302.
15. Karthika K, Rama K and Chenthilnathan A. RP-HPLC method development and validation for quantification of darunavir ethanolate in tablet dosage form. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*, 2016; 8(5): 291-296.
16. N. Charbe, Sara Baldellia, Valeria Cozzia, Simone Castoldia, Dario Cattaneo, Emilio Clementi, Development of An HPLC–UV Assay Method for The Simultaneous Quantification of Nine Antiretroviral Agents In The Plasma of HIV-Infected Patients. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis*, 2016; 6:396-403.
17. Hemant K. Jain, Umakant S. Jadhav. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for estimation of darunavir ethanolate in bulk and tablets. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2015; 7(10): 386-389.
18. Nagendrakumar AVD, Sreenivasa Rao B and Basaveswara Rao MV. Validated RP - HPLC method for the determination of Darunavir in bulk and Pharmaceutical formulation. *RJPBCS*, 2014; 5 (2): 64-73.
19. Chaudhary PG, Patel BN, Patel CN. A validated Stability-indicating High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method for Darunavir Ethanolate in Tablet Dosage Form. 2014; 2(9): 91-100.
20. Raveendra Babu G, Lakshmana Rao A and Venkateswara Rao J. Development and validation of novel HPLC method for estimation of Darunavir in pharmaceutical formulations. *IJRPC* 2013; 3 (2): 438-443.
21. Rami Reddy B.V, Jyothi G, B.S. Reddy, Raman N.V.V.S.S., Subhash Chander Reddy K, and Rambabu C. Stability-indicating HPLC method for the determination of darunavir ethanolate.

- Journal of Chromatographic Science, 2013; 51: 471-476.
22. Manisha B. Mane, Pranali J. Gaikawad, Anuja V. Patil, Aashish S. Mogale. RP-HPLC method for determination of Darunavir in bulk and pharmaceutical preparations. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.*, 2013; 21(2): 20-23.
 23. Josilenechavesruelacorrea, Cristina Helena dos Reis Serra, and Hérica Regina Nunes Salgado. Stability Study of Darunavir Ethanolate Tablets Applying A New Stability-Indicating HPLC Method. Hindawi Publishing Corporation, 2013; 3:173-177.
 24. Bhavini N. Patel, Bhanubhai N. Suhagia, Chaganbhai N. Patel. RP-HPLC method development and validation for estimation of Darunavir ethanolate in tablet dosage form. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2012; 4(3):270-273.
 25. Nagendrakumar AVD, Sreenivasa Rao and Basaveswara Rao MV, Validated RP - HPLC Method For The Determination of Darunavir In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Formulation. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences* 2014; 5(3):63-72.
 26. Satyanarayana L, Naidu S.V, Narasimha Rao M, Alok Kumar and Suresh K. The Estimation of Darunavir in Tablet dosage form by RP-HPLC., *Asian J. Res. Pharm. Sci.* 2011; 1(3): 74-76.
 27. Raveendra B. Ganduri, Ramprasad A. Lanka, Srinivasu Pamidi, Jayachandra R. Peddareddigari, JVLNS Rao. New RP-HPLC method for the determination of Darunavir in tablet dosage form, *Asian J. Pharm. Res.* 2011; 1(1): 10-14.
 28. Bhavini N. Patel, Suhagia B. N, Simultaneous Determination and Validation of Darunavir Ethanolate and Ritonavir in binary mixture by Liquid Chromatography. *International Journal of Pharmtech Research* 2012; 4(4): 1450-1456.
 29. Gupta A, Singhal P, Shrivastav PS and Mallika S. Application of a validated ultra performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry method for the quantification of Darunavir in human plasma for a bioequivalence study in Indian subjects. *J Chromatogr B.* 2011; 879(24):2443-2453.
 30. Fayet A, Beguin A, Zanolari B, Cruchon S, Guignard N, Telenti A, Cavassini M, Gunthard HF, Buclin T, Biollaz J, Rochat B and Decosterd LA. A LC-tandem MS assay for the simultaneous measurement of new antiretroviral agents: Raltegravir, Maraviroc, Darunavir, and Etravirine. *J Chromatogr B.* 2009; 877(11-12):1057-1069.
 31. Ravi Kanneti, Jaswanth K. I., Neeraja K.R, Parloop A. Bhatt, Development and Validation of LC-MS/MS Method for Determination of Darunavir in Human Plasma for Application of Clinical Pharmacokinetics. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2011; 3(5):0975-1491.
 32. Heine RT, Alderden-Los CG, Rosing H, Hillebrand MJ, Gorp ECV, Huitema AD and Beijnen JH. Fast and simultaneous determination of Darunavir and eleven other antiretroviral drugs for therapeutic drug monitoring: method development and validation for the determination of all currently approved HIV protease inhibitors and non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors in human plasma by liquid chromatography coupled with electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry. *Rapid Commun Mass Spectrom.* 2007; 21(15):2505-2514.
 33. Patel BN, Suhagia BN, Patel CN and Panchal HJ. A simple and sensitive HPTLC method for quantitative analysis of Darunavir ethanolate tablets. *J Planar Chromatogr Mod TLC.* 2011; 24(3):232-235.
 34. Leonard S, Van AS, Ivanyi T, Lazar I, Rosier J, Vanstockem M, Vermeersch H and Hoogmartens J. Development of a capillary Electrophoretic method for the separation of diastereoisomers of a new human immunodeficiency virus protease inhibitor. *Electrophoresis.* 2005; 26(3):627-632.
 35. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) harmonized tripartite guideline .Validation of analytical procedures: text and methodology Q2 (R1) ICH, Geneva, Nov (2005).